

Review

Naturopathy and Traditional Chinese Medicine in the Treatment of Emotional Stress as a Causal Factor of Autoimmune Diseases – A Narrative Review.

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Abstract

Emotional stress has been increasingly recognised as a significant contributing factor to the onset and worsening of autoimmune diseases. This review analyses the pathophysiological mechanisms by which stress negatively affects immune function, such as impairment of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, elevated secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines, autonomic nervous system (ANS) hyperactivity, and epigenetic alterations. In addition, the views of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) and naturopathy are evaluated regarding the impact of emotional stress on the onset of these conditions. TCM views stress as a disturbance of Qi and the energy balance of the organs, while naturopathy emphasises the importance of nutrition, the gut-brain-immunity axis, and emotional health. Thus, the combined approach of these therapies may potentially create new opportunities in the prevention and treatment of stress-related autoimmune diseases.

Keywords: Emotional Stress; Autoimmune Diseases; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Naturopathy.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been an increasing scientific focus on the interaction between emotional stress and autoimmune diseases. Thus, emotional stress is increasingly being recognised not only as a correlated factor, but also as a contributing element to the development of these diseases ¹.

According to Aghayan *et al.* ², the immune system is essential for the well-being and proper functioning of living organisms, being crucial for managing the body's reactions to physical injuries and infections, so that its failure can result in illness and death. In turn, dysregulation of the immune system due to stress involves cellular responses.

Furthermore, prolonged stress can induce the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin-6, which can lead to the onset of several chronic diseases ³.

Although beneficial in the short term, chronic stress becomes harmful, resulting in disorders such as depression, anxiety, and heart disease. Furthermore, chronic stress elevates pro-inflammatory cytokines, disrupts immune balance, and aggravates autoimmune conditions. It also plays a detrimental role in diseases such as Alzheimer's, asthma, cancer, coronary artery disease and others ².

Considering the potential health implications of stress, it's essential to deepen our understanding of the complex mechanisms by which stress affects immune function and the diseases that could be caused by emotional stress. Thus, this review aims to explore

the harmful effects of emotional stress as a cause of autoimmune diseases, and the role of TCM and naturopathy.

2. Methodology

This study consists of a narrative review of the literature, which aims to study the impact of emotional stress as a potential triggering or aggravating factor of autoimmune diseases, compiling information from Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) and Naturopathy.

The article selection process took place through searches in the following databases: PubMed, Scielo, ScienceDirect and Google Scholar.

The criteria for inclusion of studies were: studies written in English and Portuguese; scientific articles, systematic reviews, meta-analyses and books that addressed the link between emotional stress and autoimmunity, pathophysiological mechanisms, as well as therapeutic approaches for TCM and naturopathy. Not included were: studies that didn't specifically address the link between emotional stress and autoimmune diseases; articles with duplicate content or ambiguous data.

On the other hand, the content analysis was carried out qualitatively, collecting, comparing and integrating relevant data for the development of the work sections.

3. Emotional stress and autoimmunity

3.1. Pathophysiological mechanisms

Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (HPA) Axis Dysfunction

The HPA axis corresponds to a neurohormonal system that integrates the secretion of corticotropin-releasing hormone in the hypothalamus, adrenocorticotrophic hormone in the anterior pituitary gland and cortisol in the adrenal cortex. Therefore, the HPA axis is initiated in the hypothalamus, particularly in the parvocellular neurons of the hypothalamus, since it is in this nucleus that information from various areas of the Central Nervous System (CNS) is integrated ⁴.

In this sense, prolonged stress deregulates the HPA axis, leading to an uncontrolled release of cortisol, which reduces immunological tolerance. This dysfunction facilitates the production of autoantibodies and the activation of autoreactive T cells. Thus, studies indicate that emotional stress, by modifying immunological homeostasis, significantly increases the risk of systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) ⁵.

There are several changes in pro-inflammatory cytokines under sustained stress. In the early phase, chronic active stress dysregulates the HPA axis, the sympathoadrenal medulla, and the vagus nerve, which in turn secrete glucocorticoids, catecholamines, and acetylcholine to disrupt inflammatory cytokines in their homeostasis and downregulate proinflammatory cytokines while upregulating anti-inflammatory cytokines. In the second phase, long-lasting exposure to stress induces HPA fatigue, glucocorticoid resistance, nuclear factor kappa-B (NF- α B) activation, and negative feedback, which in turn promote pro-inflammatory cytokines. In the third phase, continuous stress further increases pro-inflammatory cytokines and ultimately causes inflammation, which can induce various diseases ⁶. On the other hand, stress promotes the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α , IFN- γ and IL-6, aggravating autoimmune diseases ⁶. This is supplemented by von Drathen *et al.* ⁷, who provide recent evidence on cytokine dysregulation in multiple sclerosis.

Additionally, stress-induced cytokine surges accelerate relapses and disability progression in multiple sclerosis (MS) ⁷.

Autonomic Nervous System and Autoimmunity

The autonomic nervous system (ANS) serves to trigger acute and chronic inflammatory responses through distinct response mechanisms. In turn, the sympathetic nervous

system (SNS) is crucial in managing the mobilization of lymphocytes into the bloodstream. This regulation occurs through the direct involvement of catecholamines with β 2AR, a beta-adrenergic receptor located on the surface of lymphocytes, illustrating the link between the immune system and the ANS. In this way, immune cells contribute to the production and release of substances commonly known as neurotransmitters and neuromodulators, such as acetylcholine, dopamine and other catecholamines, which are essential for local immune regulation and for more complex neuroimmunomodulatory circuits⁸.

According to Lai *et al.*⁹, emotional trauma causes hyperactivation of the SNS, promoting an imbalance in the lymphocyte balance in which Th17 and Treg cells direct it towards a pro-inflammatory state. This phenomenon has been particularly observed in MS and rheumatoid arthritis (RA).

Genetic and Epigenetic Modifications

Epigenetics denotes heritable modifications in gene expression that occur without changes in the DNA sequence. This links genetic influences and harmful environmental exposures to toxins, which are considered significant elements for the formation of the organism's phenotype, as they modify chromatin remodelling, DNA methylation and RNA synthesis¹⁰.

In this context, anxiety is characterized as an unpleasant physical experience and psychological condition and is categorized as a physiological reaction to some form of threat, so that this adaptive mechanism aims to increase the individual's survival and safety. Its origin is complex and unique for each person, involving a complex interaction of genetic, environmental, social and biological elements¹⁰.

According to Schlosser *et al.*¹⁰, epigenetic changes induced by chronic emotional stress help explain the predisposition to autoimmune diseases. In this context, increased methylation of immune system regulatory genes has been associated with childhood trauma, predisposing individuals to diseases such as MS. For example, FOXP3 gene methylation affects regulatory T cell function, while hypermethylation of glucocorticoid receptor genes impairs HPA axis regulation, contributing to autoimmune vulnerability.

Moreover, according to Oliveira¹¹, the set of epigenetic alterations, known as the epigenome, is indicative of the cell type and offers mechanisms of variation and specialisation, regulating the accessibility of genetic information to the cellular machinery. Problems in the establishment or maintenance of epigenetic marks can lead to the incorrect activation or suppression of different genes and alter typical cellular physiology, resulting in the appearance of diseases.

3.2. Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) Perspective

Stress is a natural response that includes physical elements and/or psychological aspects, triggered by psychophysiological changes that occur when an individual is faced with situations that bother, scare, stimulate or disconcert them, or even make them happy. In this sense, stress represents a condition of mental and physical exhaustion that leads to an interruption in the general functioning of the human being¹².

In TCM, emotional stress is considered one of the main intrinsic causes of diseases, as emotional imbalance disturbs the flow of Qi (energy) and Blood, creating pathogenic conditions that aggravate autoimmune diseases¹³.

Thus, TCM is based on the idea that there's an integrated energy structure in the physical body, allowing energy to flow through pathways known as meridians. Meridians function as conductors that connect the different energy systems of the body, allowing the circulation of vital energies (Qi) or pathogenic energies (Xie), which directly affect the body and contain specific points. These points, when activated, reorganise the energy flow throughout the body¹².

Therefore, the occurrence of diseases is invariably linked to the disorganisation of the functional energy that governs and energises the meridians. This comprehensive system, which has evolved through experimentation and refinement over thousands of years, can be harmonised through acupuncture. Consequently, the Chinese realise that the general functioning of the organism and mind depends on the adequate flow of energies or the organism's vital force, our Qi ¹².

Emotional Stress as a Dysfunction of Organic Systems

- Liver Qi Stagnation

Anger and continuous emotional repression affect the liver, which is responsible for the flow of Qi ¹². Additionally, stagnation can lead to movement disorders. For example, liver qi stagnation, which can originate from emotional stagnation, can cause increased liver yang activity, resulting in anxiety. Thus, stagnation of Qi can also cause the accumulation of sputum, which can hinder the free flow of the spirit, resulting in anxiety ¹⁴.

In common patterns of autoimmune diseases such as lupus and RA, liver Qi stagnation is thought to progress to blood stasis and heat ¹⁵.

- Spleen Qi Deficiency

According to Jiang ¹⁶, excessive worry and anxiety harm the spleen, compromising its ability to generate and control blood. In turn, this deficit leads to the formation of dampness and phlegm, factors often considered precursors to autoimmune inflammation.

- Kidney Yin Deficiency

Fear and chronic stress consume the kidney Yin, causing internal heat and Yin deficit. Imbalances of this type are often associated with autoimmune thyroid diseases, such as Hashimoto's thyroiditis. In turn, the main symptoms of patients with Hashimoto's thyroiditis include weakness, irritability, lack of appetite, neck discomfort and decreased memory ¹⁷.

- Heart Qi Stagnation

In TCM, stagnation of heart qi is often associated with emotional stress, particularly when feelings such as anxiety, sadness or frustration are repressed or prolonged. The heart, which contains the Shen (mind/spirit), is immediately affected by this disharmony, leading to symptoms such as tightness in the chest, palpitations, insomnia, frequent sighing and moodiness. This energetic obstruction is generally aggravated by continuous emotional tension and lack of emotional expression ¹².

- Lung Qi Stagnation

In TCM, the lung is linked to feelings of sadness and grief, and when these feelings persist or are not processed properly, they can result in stagnation of Lung Qi. This emotional state affects the normal circulation of energy, complicating both energetic and physical breathing, and can manifest as tightness in the chest, short or labored breathing, weak voice, melancholy and a tendency to cry easily ¹⁸.

The TCM approach

- Phytotherapy

The Gan Mai Da Zao Tang formula consists of three primary herbs: Radix Glycyrrhiza uralensis Fisch (commonly known as Gan Cao – liquorice), Triticum aestivum Levis (Fu Xiao Mai – wheat), and Fructus Zizyphus jujubae (Da Zao – jujube). Gan Cao, characterised by its sweet flavour and neutral quality, serves to nourish the Qi of the Heart and Spleen, in addition to having antispasmodic characteristics. Fu Xiao Mai, known for its sweet and slightly salty flavour as well as its fresh quality, helps nourish heart Yin and promote mental tranquillity. Da Zao, which has a sweet taste and warm quality, nourishes Qi and blood, soothes the Liver, and moistens the internal organs (Zang). Therefore, the main therapeutic benefits of the formula include: nourishing the heart, pacifying the Shen

(Spirit), harmonizing the Middle Jiao, tonifying the spleen Qi, and relieving emotional restlessness¹⁹.

Also, Xiao Yao San is a traditional Chinese medicine formulation that has been widely shown to effectively relieve depression in clinical studies. However, the findings are not definitive²⁰.

Additionally, Gui Pi Tang is a notable formula for persistent Qi and blood deficiency, as well as bleeding problems associated with these, resulting from stress and overexertion. The formula mainly focuses on spleen and heart blood, but also treats liver blood deficiency. Its use is particularly recommended for menstrual bleeding: it can be used for excessive bleeding, prolonged bleeding, painful, irregular or absent menstrual cycles²¹.

- Acupuncture

Acupuncture is a traditional Chinese technique that involves stimulating specific points on the body to restore energy balance, known as Qi, and improve emotional health. Thus, acupuncture points such as Taichong (LR3) and Sanyinjiao (SP6), located on the feet and legs, are often used to manage the flow of Qi and calm the Shen (spirit), especially in stressful situations^{22,23}.

- Lifestyle Changes

According to Pölönen *et al.*²⁴, practices such as Qigong and meditation help to balance emotions. Qigong is a form of meditative movement exercise that involves conscious movement, breath control and focusing attention. Thus, meditative movement practices combine specific movement patterns, breathing techniques and mental focus to achieve cognitive and emotional changes in the human being, the understanding of which could shed new light on the interrelationship between the body and the embodied mind, especially to avoid stressful situations

3.3. The Naturopathic Approach

Naturopathy highlights the interaction between mental and physical health, emphasising the role of emotional well-being in regulating the immune system²⁵.

In this context, naturopathy, which is a comprehensive approach to health and well-being, highlights the body's inherent ability to heal itself when the appropriate conditions are met. Thus, preventive strategies in naturopathy provide a comprehensive framework for promoting well-being and preventing disease²⁶.

In naturopathy, it's believed that health is not simply the absence of disease, but rather a state of balance that encompasses physical, mental and emotional well-being. For this reason, naturopathic practitioners focus on treating the root causes of health problems rather than just relieving the symptoms. Consequently, prevention and well-being gain importance in maintaining balance and protecting health²⁶.

Gut-Brain-Immunity Axis

As we look at the harmony of the gut microbiome, methods to balance microbial communities through dietary changes provide realistic solutions for addressing gastrointestinal health. In addition, there are innovative clinical methods, such as specific probiotics, faecal microbiota transplantation and neurointestinal treatments, indicating a transformative change in health care. These developments represent not only a scientific breakthrough but also pave the way for personalised and effective therapies for gastrointestinal diseases. In this collaborative relationship between science and health, intestinal microbiota actively modulates immune function and systemic health^{7,27}.

However, emotional stress alters the intestinal microbiota, increasing intestinal permeability, allowing bacterial endotoxins to enter the circulation and triggering autoimmune reactions. Therefore, microbiota-focused dietary changes have demonstrated benefits in both emotional well-being and autoimmune symptoms²⁷.

Emotional Health and Inflammatory Markers

Depressive symptoms and autoimmune activity have been associated with high levels of inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP) and IL-6. Thus, reducing emotional distress leads to a decrease in disease severity by reducing these markers ²⁸.

However, it's important to highlight that the addition of pure ellagic acid leads to remarkable improvements in several factors related to depression among MS patients, observing a significant reduction in BDI-II levels along with reductions in cortisol levels, interferon- γ (IFN- δ) and indoleamine 2, 3-dioxygenase gene expression. Furthermore, ellagic acid may also influence immune response functions, leading to increased Th2 activity and decreased Th1 activity, with the upregulation of Th2 cells being particularly advantageous in the context of depression ²⁸.

Holistic Interventions

Holistic interventions have demonstrated their effectiveness in improving physical and emotional balance, especially in the context of stress management and modulation of the inflammatory response.

Phytotherapy, for example, uses adaptogenic plants such as rhodiola and ashwagandha, which are recognised for their ability to reduce levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines and regulate cortisol, the main hormone associated with stress. These plants help the body adapt more effectively to stress and maintain homeostasis ²⁹.

Mind-body therapies, including yoga, mindfulness meditation, and biofeedback, play a vital role in regulating the HPA axis, which is essential in the body's response to stress. These practices encourage deep relaxation and tension relief, leading to decreased SNS activation and promoting a more balanced reaction to stress ³⁰.

Furthermore, an anti-inflammatory diet with foods rich in antioxidants and omega-3 fatty acids positively influences the reduction of chronic inflammation triggered by stress. These nutrients help fight free radicals and protect cells, contributing to reducing inflammation and improving overall well-being ³¹.

Therefore, integrating these methods offers an effective strategy for restoring balance to the body and mind, promoting a healthier and more resilient approach to stress.

4. Scientific Evidence Supports the Link Between Stress and Autoimmunity

As previously reported in this study, several mechanisms explain the link between stress and autoimmune diseases. Table 1 summarises the role of stress and therapeutic strategies.

Table 1. Impact of stress in autoimmune diseases and potential therapeutic approaches.

Dis-ease	Stress Impact	Therapeutic Strategy	Reference(s)
MS	Increases relapse risk	Psychosocial treatments (CBT, mindfulness)	7
RA	Worsens disease activity	Stress reduction, emotional support	15
SLE	Associated with trauma and severity	Coping strategies, psychosocial support	32
T1D	Raises glucose levels via SNS activation	Stress management interventions	33
AS	Elevates pain and inflammation	Relaxation strategies, psychological support	Summarised from manuscript content

4.1. Multiple Sclerosis (MS)

Stress greatly increases the chances of illness and relapse. As noted by von Drathen *et al.*⁷, stress constitutes a primary risk factor, and research indicates that stress management improves clinical outcomes. Psychosocial treatments, including cognitive behavioural therapy, mindfulness, and relaxation methods, have been shown to be effective in reducing the occurrence of relapses and improving patients' quality of life. Furthermore, approaches that promote emotional well-being can influence the immune response, positively affecting the progression of MS disease.

4.2. Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA)

Patients diagnosed with RA have a higher prevalence of mental health disorders when compared to the general population. Emotional distress and RA are believed to influence each other in a bidirectional manner. Longitudinal studies demonstrate that reduced stress is directly associated with decreased disease activity¹⁵.

4.3. Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE)

Traumatic life events are strongly associated with the onset and exacerbation of lupus. Strategies for coping with trauma help to reduce disease severity and autoantibody levels. Enhancing positive psychosocial factors and reducing negative psychosocial factors may alleviate perceived detrimental stress, which may improve outcomes in SLE, even in individuals with a history of prior trauma who may be more susceptible to stressful situations³².

4.4. Type 1 Diabetes (T1D)

Stress significantly affects the control of type 1 diabetes (T1D), impacting both the physiological and emotional facets of the condition. Stress stimulates the SNS, raising cortisol and adrenaline levels, which increases glucose production by the liver and decreases the effectiveness of insulin, leading to increased blood glucose levels. Furthermore, psychological stress resulting from ongoing disease management can result in anxiety and depression, forming a harmful cycle that worsens glycemic control³³.

4.5. Ankylosing Spondylitis (AS)

Psychological stress is closely linked to the worsening of AS, affecting both the intensity of pain and the inflammatory activity of the disease. Research indicates that individuals with AS have high levels of stress, anxiety, and depression, which are positively related to clinical measures. This connection is reciprocal: stress worsens AS symptoms and, conversely, functional limitations and persistent pain increase psychological distress. Neuroimmunological processes, including activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, may shed light on this relationship, implying that stress management—through psychological interventions and relaxation strategies—may be helpful not only for emotional health but also for controlling inflammation and disease progression.

5. Discussion

The connection between emotional stress and autoimmune diseases is supported by several scientific and therapeutic means, as demonstrated in this article. Several researchers come together to analyse pathophysiological mechanisms and integrative strategies to understand and alleviate this problem.

HPA axis dysfunction, as described by Iturriaga *et al.*⁴, serves as a crucial physiological basis for understanding how chronic stress affects immunity. Mismanaged cortisol secretion, highlighted by Blasbalg *et al.*⁵, reinforces the argument that emotional stress can act as a catalyst for the activation of autoimmune cells, similar to what occurs in systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE).

Similarly, increased release of pro-inflammatory cytokines during periods of chronic stress, according to research by Tian *et al.* ⁶, illustrates a damaging cycle of inflammation that sustains and exacerbates autoimmune diseases. This mechanism has particular significance in multiple sclerosis, as demonstrated by von Drathen *et al.* ⁷, who relate cytokine elevations to relapses and clinical decline.

In turn, the data from Schlosser *et al.* ¹⁰ and Oliveira ¹¹ on epigenetics are especially pertinent to elucidate how emotional stress permanently modifies immunological genetic expression, making individuals susceptible to autoimmunity — particularly those with a history of psychological trauma in childhood.

From a TCM perspective, stress is analysed as an energetic disturbance that interrupts the movement of Qi and Blood, a fundamental principle of TCM. Bastos ¹², Doria *et al.* ¹³ and Silva ¹⁴ illustrate how dysfunctions in several organs (liver, spleen, kidneys, heart and lungs) are linked to negative emotional patterns and physical manifestations of immunity.

Chinese herbal medicine also shows significant therapeutic promise. Formulations such as Gan Mai Da Zao Tang ¹⁹, Xiao Yao San ²⁰ and Gui Pi Tang ²¹ indicate efficacy in emotional and energetic modulation, being relevant in the treatment of both emotional symptoms and autoimmune manifestations.

The naturopathic perspective, as explained by Manoharan *et al.* ²⁵ and Serpente ²⁶, emphasises health as systemic balance. The importance of the gut-brain-immunity axis, promoted by Shang *et al.* ²⁷, illustrates how stress-induced changes in the gut microbiota impact immune health. Furthermore, the role of systemic inflammation caused by negative emotions is supported by Hajiluian *et al.* ²⁸, who highlight the link between inflammatory markers and emotional disorders.

Additionally, integrative and holistic therapies, including the application of adaptogenic plants ²⁹, relaxation strategies and anti-inflammatory diets ^{30,31}, are considered effective approaches for managing stress and autoimmunity, promoting not only symptomatic relief but also a better quality of life.

Finally, clinical evidence linking stress to autoimmune diseases — specifically MS, RA, and SLE — strengthens the need for psychosocial interventions as a vital component of treatment. As pointed out by von Drathen *et al.* ⁷ and Sweeney *et al.* ¹⁵, stress management directly influences immune modulation and clinical progression of autoimmune diseases.

5.1. Integrative Perspectives: Biomedical and Energetic Models

This subsection explores the potential alignment between biomedical immunological mechanisms and TCM energetic interpretations. For instance, HPA axis dysfunction and cortisol dysregulation in biomedical models are viewed in TCM as disruptions in Kidney and Liver Qi balance, leading to systemic vulnerability. Similarly, the biomedical concept of elevated pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-6 and TNF-alpha, aligns with TCM interpretations of 'internal heat' or 'Yang excess', which are understood to aggravate autoimmune conditions. Furthermore, Qi stagnation as described in TCM, especially in the Liver, resonates with the biomedical recognition of autonomic nervous system imbalance and stress-induced inflammatory states.

Integrating these paradigms may provide a holistic understanding of autoimmunity, combining molecular evidence with energetic frameworks to inform prevention and treatment. Such integration could support the development of comprehensive therapies that address both the physiological and energetic disturbances underlying autoimmune diseases, offering innovative avenues for patient-centred care ^{23,27}.

6. Conclusion

There is strong scientific evidence supporting the causal relationship between emotional imbalance and autoimmune diseases; therefore, focusing on emotional control, stress management, and holistic approaches based on TCM and Naturopathy offers promising avenues for the treatment and prevention of these conditions. However, further multidisciplinary studies are needed to integrate these approaches into clinical practice.

There remains considerable ambiguity regarding the origins of autoimmune disorders, and it's possible that a crucial understanding lies in the interaction between these diseases and mental health. Thus, subsequent research efforts should further investigate the links between various autoimmune diseases and early mental health antecedents.

In summary, this review emphasises the importance of emotional stress as a key factor in the initiation and exacerbation of autoimmune diseases, through the disruption of physiological systems such as the HPA, the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, the hyperactivity of the ANS, and epigenetic changes that impair the immune response. In this way, TCM and Naturopathy offer complementary points of view to the biomedical perspective, encouraging holistic methods centred on energy balance, emotional management and the promotion of a healthy lifestyle. By addressing the emotional and systemic origins of disease, these therapies may play a significant role in the prevention and treatment of stress-related autoimmune diseases. Therefore, incorporating these modalities into the clinical setting may represent a promising advancement in general health care, especially for individuals susceptible to the effects of chronic stress.

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